

INTERACTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE USAGE TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. *Today, this article focuses on the reader, student, his personality and unique inner world. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose methods and forms of organization of students whose educational activities are optimally compatible with the goal of personal development. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in institutes, lyceums, colleges and vocational schools has been raised more and more.*

Keywords: *english, independent language learning, educational technologies, project, interest, activity, interactive methods, internet resource, communicative approach, project method.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, the main attention is focused on the student, his personality and unique inner world. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose methods and forms of organization of students whose educational activities are optimally compatible with the set goal of personal development. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in schools is increasing rising. This is not only new technical tools, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the educational process. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is to form and develop the communicative culture of schoolchildren, to teach them to learn a foreign language in practice. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose methods and forms of organization of educational activities students that optimally correspond to the set goal of personal development. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in schools is increasing rising. It is not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the educational process. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is to form and develop the communicative culture of schoolchildren, to teach them to practice a foreign language.

Teaching and learning English during research is popular methods, internet sources were used. During the writing of the article, the principles of theoretical deductive conclusion, analysis and synthesis, logicity were used.

The task of the teacher is to create conditions for practical mastery of the language for each student, to choose such teaching methods that allow each student to demonstrate his activity and creativity. The task of the teacher is to activate the cognitive activity of the student in the process of teaching foreign languages. In partnership modern pedagogical technologies such as learning, project methodology, use of new information technologies, Internet resources help to implement a person-oriented approach in the educational process, individualization and differentiation of teaching, taking into account the abilities of children, their level of learning provides Forms of working with computer training programs in foreign language classes include: learning vocabulary; practice pronunciation; teaching dialogic and monologic speech; teaching to write; development of grammatical events.

The possibilities of using Internet resources are huge. The Global Internet provides conditions for students and teachers located in any part of the world to get any necessary information: regional geographical materials, news in the life of young people, articles from newspapers and magazines, etc.

It is possible to solve a number of didactic problems using the Internet in English classes: formation of reading skills and qualifications using global network materials; improving the writing ability of schoolchildren; filling students' vocabulary; formation of students' motivation to learn English. In addition, this work belongs to schoolchildren aims to explore the possibilities of Internet technologies to expand horizons, establish and maintain business relationships and contacts with peers in English-speaking countries. Participation of students in Internet tests, quizzes, contests, Olympiads, etc they can participate in correspondence, conversations, video conferences, etc. with their peers in other countries.

Students can get information about the problem they are currently working on in the project. The meaningful basis of mass computerization is related to the fact that the modern computer is an effective tool for optimizing the conditions of mental work, in general, in any of its forms. One characteristic of the computer that defines its use as a tool for teaching others and as an aid in the acquisition of knowledge is its inanimate nature.

The machine can be "friendly" and sometimes "supportive" with the user, but it will never show signs of anger or let you feel bored. In this sense, the use of computers is perhaps most useful in individualizing some aspects of teaching. The main thing is to learn a foreign language at school its goal is to form communicative competence, all other goals (education, training, development) are implemented in the process of implementing this main goal. Communicative approach includes communication training and formation of intercultural influence, which is the basis of Internet activity. The Internet has no meaning outside of communication is an international multinational, cross-cultural society, whose life is based on the electronic communication of millions of people in the world, talking at the same time - it is the largest conversation in terms of the number of participants and the volume that has taken place. To him in class participation in a foreign language, we create a real communication model.

At present, communication, interactivity, authenticity of communication, language learning in cultural context, autonomy and humanitarianism of education are given priority. These principles allow the development of intercultural competence as a component of communicative competence. The ultimate goal of teaching foreign languages is to freely navigate in a foreign language environment and is to teach the ability to respond adequately in different situations, i.e. contact Today, new methods using Internet resources are against traditional foreign language teaching. To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real, real-life situations that stimulate the learning of the material and develop adequate behavior (that is, the principle of communication authenticity called).

New technologies, in particular the Internet, are trying to correct this error is doing Communicative approach is a strategy that simulates communication aimed at conscious understanding of the material and methods of working with it, creating psychological and linguistic preparation for communication. It is not particularly difficult for the user to implement a communicative approach on the Internet. A communicative task should invite students to discuss a problem or question, students not only exchange information, but also evaluate it. It is possible to distinguish this approach from other types of educational activities the main criterion is that

students independently choose linguistic units to form their thoughts. In the communicative approach, the use of the Internet is very well encouraged: its purpose is to interest students in learning a foreign language by accumulating and expanding their knowledge and experience.

One of the main requirements for teaching foreign languages using Internet resources is to create interaction in the lesson, which is usually called interactivity in the methodology. Interactivity is "combining, coordinating, and complementing communicative goals and resulting efforts by means of speech." By teaching real language, the Internet helps build speaking skills and abilities, as well as vocabulary and grammar sincere interest in teaching and, therefore, ensures efficiency. Interactivity not only creates real situations from life, but also forces students to give appropriate answers to them in a foreign language.

One of the technologies that provide student-centered education is the project method as a method of developing creativity, knowledge activity, and independence. The typology of projects is diverse. Projects can be divided into monoprosjects, collective, oral, concrete, written and Internet projects. In actual practice, it is often necessary to deal with research projects, mixed projects with creative, practice-oriented and informational features. Project work is a multifaceted approach to language learning, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. The project method helps to develop active independent thinking of students and directs them to joint research work. In my opinion, project-based learning teaches children to cooperate, and learning to cooperate inculcates moral values such as mutual aid and empathy, builds creativity, and activates students. In general, the inseparability of education and training in the process of teaching the project observed.

The project method develops students' communication skills, culture of behavior, the ability to form thoughts concisely and easily, tolerance of the opinions of communication partners, the ability to receive information from various sources, process using modern computer technologies, contribute to the emergence of natural needs creates a friendly language environment and facilitates communication in a foreign language.

The project form of the work gives students the accumulated knowledge on the subject it is one of the most relevant technologies that allow to use it. Students expand their horizons, the limits of knowledge of the language, gain experience in its practical use, learn to listen and hear speech in a foreign language, understand each other when defending projects. Children work with reference books, dictionaries, computers, and thus create the possibility of direct contact with the real language, which does not provide language learning in the classroom only with the help of textbooks.

Working on a project is a creative process. The student searches for a solution to the problem independently or under the guidance of the teacher, which requires not only knowledge of the language, but also a large amount of subject knowledge, creative, communicative and intellectual skills.

In the course of foreign languages, the project method can be used within the program materials on almost any subject. Working on projects develops imagination, fantasy, creative thinking, independence and other personal qualities.

Language teaching programs on computers and phones are also a good help for language teaching at the primary and secondary levels. Talk (English speaking practice), Daily English, Learn English (English master), How to speak real English are examples. These programs are structured in such a way that they include reading, listening, and test sections.

Another good way to practice is to record the new words you have learned and listen to them in your spare time. In addition, showing more movies and cartoons with subtitles in English is also an effective way to teach the language.

Speech skills in trainings during the educational process sufficient attention should be paid to formation and development of social flexibility. In addition, the success of each lesson in education largely depends on the correct organization of the training. The lesson should be based on the creative cooperation of the teacher and the student. Only then will students be able to think independently and will be educated.

The main idea is to create conditions for active joint activity of students in various educational conditions. Children join groups of 3-4 people, they are given one task, while everyone's role is discussed. Each student is responsible not only for the result of his work, but also for the result of the whole group. Therefore, weak students try to find out what they do not understand from weak ones, and strong students try to give the weak students a thorough understanding of the task. And the whole class benefits because the gaps are closed together.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The introduction of information technologies into education greatly diversifies the process of information perception and processing. Thanks to the computer, the Internet and multimedia, a unique opportunity was created for students to learn a large amount of information with further analysis and sorting. The motivational basis of educational activity is also expanding significantly. In the context of using multimedia, students get information from newspapers, television, conduct interviews and conduct teleconferences.

The main criteria for assessing the level of knowledge of a foreign language in language portfolio technology is the test. The priority direction of this technology is to direct the educational process from the teacher to the student. The student, in turn, is consciously responsible for the results of his educational activity. The above technology leads to the gradual formation of students' skills to learn information independently. In general, the language portfolio is multifunctional and contributes to the development of multilingualism.

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